

A Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship Study of the Antifungal Properties of some Cinnamic Acid Derivatives using Lipophilicity ($\log P$), Second Order Molecular Connectivity ($^2\chi^v$) and Information Content (1IC)

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The preparation of nineteen structural analogues of ethyl *p*-methoxycinnamate (EPMC) and their minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) against *Trichophyton rubrum* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* are described. Quantitative structure activity relationship (QSAR) was studied constructing regression equations involving lipophilicity ($\log P$), second order molecular connectivity ($^2\chi^v$) and first order information content (1IC) of these compounds with $\log$ (MIC) of the test organisms. The study indicated a difference in the mechanism of action between *T. rubrum* and *S. cerevisiae* and suggest a steric and an electronic parameter are involved simultaneously for the observed antifungal activity with *T. rubrum*.

In the previous communications^{1,2} we reported the presence of a broad spectrum antifungal compound from the dried rhizome of *Curcuma zedoaria Roscoe*. The compound was purified and its chemical structure was determined as *trans*-ethyl *p*-methoxycinnamate (EPMC)³. This 'lead' compound inhibits *in vitro* the growth of *Trichophyton rubrum*, *Aspergillus nigr*e, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Epidermophyton floccosum* at a concentration $<10 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$; *A. fumigatus*, *Penicillium perpurogenum*, *Trignopsis variabilis*, *Microsporium gypseum*, *Sclerotium rolfisii*, *Geotrichum candidae*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Helminthosporium oryzae* at a concentration $<25 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and *Candida krusei* and *T. mentagrophytes* at a concentration $<50 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. In the present communication, we report the preparation of different structural analogues of this lead compound and their minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) against *T. rubrum* and *S. cerevisiae*. In order to formulate a rational method for the development of the effective antifungal compounds of this class and their nature of action on test organisms, we have undertaken a QSAR study of this series of congeners using some molecular parameters such as $\log P$, molecular connectivity of second order ($^2\chi^v$) and an information topological index, the first order information content (1IC) of the molecule.

Experimental

The 'lead' compound and the acid obtained on its hydrolysis were isolated, purified and/or syn-

thesised as described earlier³. Cinnamic acid was obtained commercially, and other different structural analogues of the 'lead' compound were directly purchased or synthesised as described in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SYNTHESIS OF DIFFERENT STRUCTURAL ANALOGUES OF *trans*-EPMC

Sl no	Compd	Method of synthesis, m p. and reference
1	Cinnamic acid	Commercial (E Merck), m p $133 \pm 1^\circ$
2	<i>trans-p</i> -Methoxycinnamic acid	By condensation of anisaldehyde, malonic acid and pyridine - heated on a steam-bath for 4 h m p $172 \pm 1^\circ$
3	<i>trans-p</i> -Methoxymethylcinnamate	By esterification of 2 with methanol saturated with HCl gas, made faintly alkaline at 0° with Na_2CO_3 , and extracted with ether, m p $88 \pm 1^\circ$
4	<i>trans-p</i> -Methoxyethylcinnamate	Synthesised as 3, using ethanol instead of methanol, m p $48 - 50^\circ$
5	<i>p</i> -Hydroxycinnamic acid	By heating <i>p</i> -hydroxybenzaldehyde, malonic acid and pyridine on a water-bath for 5 h, m p $207 \pm 1^\circ$ (Refs 4, 5)
6	<i>p</i> -Acetylcinnamic acid	By condensation of <i>p</i> -acetylbenzaldehyde with malonic acid and pyridine, m p $200 \pm 2^\circ$ (Refs 4 and 5)
7	3,4-Dihydroxycinnamic acid	Synthesised as per Refs. 4 and 5, m p $194 \pm 1^\circ$
8	3,4-Dimethoxycinnamic acid	Synthesised as per Refs. 4 and 5, m p $180 \pm 1^\circ$

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(Table 1 contd.)

9	3,4-Diacetylcinnamic acid	Synthesised as per Refs. 4 and 5. All the aldehydes were converted to the corresponding acids as per Refs 4-6
10.	Ferulic acid	By hydrolysis of acetylferulic acid with 10% KOH on a steam-bath for 4 h, m p 170±1°
11	Acetylferulic acid	By the condensation of vanilline acetate, malonic acid and pyridine, m p 64-8°
12	Isoferulic acid	By hydrolysis of acetylisoferulic acid with 10% KOH on a steam-bath for 4 h, m p 230±1°
13	Acetylisoferulic acid	By condensation of malonic acid, isovanilline acetate and pyridine, m.p. 201±2°
14.	3-Bromo-4-hydroxy-cinnamic acid	p-Hydroxybenzaldehyde was brominated to 3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde by bromine in glacial acetic acid; the product purified by chromatography on silica gel and converted to the corresponding acid (Refs. 4 and 5), m.p. 179±2°
15.	3,5-Dibromo-4-hydroxy-cinnamic acid	Synthesised as compd. sl. no. 14, m.p. 244±2°
16.	3,4-Methylenedioxy-cinnamic acid	By condensation of piperonal, malonic acid and pyridine by heating on a steam-bath for 4 h and the resulting solid crystallised from 95% alcohol, m.p. 234°
17	o-Methoxycinnamaldehyde	o-Methoxybenzaldehyde was converted to o-methoxycinnamaldehyde as per Ref 6, b.p. 210°
18.	o-Methoxycinnamic acid	Condensation of compound sl. no. 17 with malonic acid and pyridine, m.p. 45±1°
19.	cis-Ethyl-p-methoxycinnamate	By uv irradiation of compound sl. no. 3 for 30 min, m.p. 53±2° (Ref. 7)
20.	Methoxy-β-phenyl-propionic acid	By reduction of p-methoxycinnamic acid with sodium amalgam (2.5%), m.p. 47° (Ref. 8)

Mathematical aspect :

Calculation of lipophilicity (log P, octanol/water) : Lipophilicity (log P, octanol/water) of a compound plays a very important role in the transport across the biological membrane. log P values of the test compounds were calculated by substituting groups for hydrogen (π-system) or summing the appropriate structural element (Fragment System) according to Nys and Rekker⁹ and Hansch *et al.*¹⁰.

Calculation of second order valence molecular connectivity (²χ^v) : For cinnamic acid and its derivatives, ²χ^v was calculated utilising the equation,

$${}^2\chi^v = \sum (\delta_i^v \delta_j^v \delta_k^v)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$$

where, i, j and k are atoms bonded in sequence or in a path and the sum is over all distinct sets of two edge paths¹¹.

Calculation of information content of first order neighbourhood atoms (¹IC) from the molecular

graph : The first order topological information content of different molecular graphs can be computed according to the formalism of Sarkar *et al.*¹². If G is a non-hydrogen suppressed molecular graph with vertex set X(G) and A_i (i=1, 2, 3..... K) is a partition of X(G), then the probability scheme is given by

$$\left(\begin{matrix} A_1, A_2, \dots, A_k \\ P_1, P_2, \dots, P_k \end{matrix} \right)$$

where, P_i=n_i/n, and n_i and n are the cardinalities of A_i and X(G), respectively. The information content (¹IC)¹³ considering the class partition of vertices with respect to first order neighbour is given by Shannon's formula¹⁴,

$$IC[X(G)] = - \sum_k p_i \log_2 p_i \text{ bits}$$

the logarithm is taken at a base 2 to measure the information in bits.

Calculations of ²χ^v and ¹IC for EPMC and its structural analogues were done with the help of a Burroughs 6738 computer (Burroughs standard package program BASIS) at Regional Research Centre, Jadavpur University.

Experimental

Biological study :

A *Trichophyton rubrum* strain originally isolated from clinical material was obtained from the School of Tropical Medicine, Calcutta. The fungus was maintained on Sabouraud's dextrose agar slant (pH 6.7±0.1). *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, a non-pathogenic yeast, was maintained on peptone-yeast extract agar slant (pH 5.4±0.1) (This unicellular non-pathogenic fungus also belongs to ascomycetes like *T. rubrum*, but it is much easier to work with it as it is a fast growing one and the assay results with this organisms are highly reproducible).

Determination of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) : Sterile double strength Sabouraud's broth was dispensed in a series of pyrex tubes (15×1.5 cm), each tube receiving 2.5 ml of the broth. All the tubes were seeded with the spore suspension (0.1 ml) of *T. rubrum* prepared according to Dhar and Bose¹⁵. For *S. cerevisiae* a 0.1 ml of 24 h old culture grown in peptone yeast extract medium containing about 10⁶ spores/ml was used as inoculum. The compounds in ethanolic solution were added at graded concentration (1-300 μg ml⁻¹) to different tubes in the series. The control series received the corresponding amount of ethanol. The volume of liquid medium in each tube was made up to 5 ml with sterile distilled water. The tubes were incubated at 32±2° for 5 day when the appreciable growth of *T. rubrum* was visible in the control tubes. For *S. cerevisiae*, the tubes were incubated at 37° for 48 h.

Results

The results are presented in Tables 3 and 4 and in equations (1-6). Both linear and non-linear

regression analysis using either of $\log P$, ${}^2\chi^v$ or $1/{}^1IC$ to rationalise the congeners yielded no significant correlation. A multiparametric approach utilising ${}^2\chi^v$ and $1/{}^1IC$ with $\log (MIC)$ yielded statistically significant correlation for *T. rubrum*. However, no such significant correlation could be obtained for $\log (MIC)$ for *S. cerevisiae* with neither ${}^2\chi^v$ and $1/{}^1IC$, nor with ${}^2\chi^v$ and $\log P$, nor with $1/{}^1IC$ and $\log P$. For valence molecular connectivity (${}^m\chi^v$) and information content (nIC), where m and n indicate the order of the neighbourhood considered, the values were calculated with the help of Burrough's computer upto $m=n=5$ and all these higher order parameter values were then fitted in the computer study for constructing regression equations involving these values and the respective $\log (MIC)$ values. Only the best-fit multiparametric regression equations are presented in Table 2.

Discussion

Due to a limited number of successful antifungal compounds available for the treatment, there is always a pressing need for new antifungal substances to combat with the infection caused by different pathogenic fungi and yeasts. Griesofulvin, the most

TABLE 2

$\log (MIC) = 0.3806 + 0.8471 ({}^2\chi^v) - 0.6867 (\log P)$ <i>S. cerevisiae</i> $n = 13 \quad r = 0.6766 \quad S = 0.401 \quad F_{2,10} = 4.2216$	(1)
$\log (MIC) = 6.3282 - 0.0766 ({}^2\chi^v) - 14.0485 (1/{}^1IC)$ <i>S. cerevisiae</i> $n = 13 \quad r = 0.6907 \quad S = 0.3938 \quad F_{2,10} = 4.5609$	(2)
$\log (MIC) = 6.2597 - 0.1658 (\log P) - 13.133 (1/{}^1IC)$ <i>S. cerevisiae</i> $n = 13 \quad r = 0.715 \quad S = 0.3808 \quad F_{2,10} = 5.2273$	(3)
$\log (MIC) = 0.4749 + 1.2492 ({}^2\chi^v) - 1.1758 (\log P)$ <i>T. rubrum</i> $n = 17 \quad r = 0.7471 \quad S = 0.5047 \quad F_{2,14} = 8.8428$	(4)
$\log (MIC) = 7.5357 + 0.9152 ({}^2\chi^v) - 24.7499 (1/{}^1IC)$ <i>T. rubrum</i> $n = 17 \quad r = 0.8582 \quad S = 0.3897 \quad F_{2,14} = 19.5671$	(5)
$\log (MIC) = 9.5605 - 0.404 (\log P) - 20.645 (1/{}^1IC)$ <i>T. rubrum</i> $n = 17 \quad r = 0.7977 \quad S = 0.4579 \quad F_{2,14} = 12.237$	(6)

n = number of data points, r = the correlation coefficient, S = standard deviation, F = F -ratio between the variance of observed and calculated values.

commonly used antifungal agent available, has been reported to cause some adverse effects in its long-term use^{20,21}. Moreover, as compounds available for clinical purpose are very few, the chance of

TABLE 3—VALUES OF $\log P$, ${}^2\chi^v$ AND $1/{}^1IC$ AND THE $\log (MIC)$ OF DIFFERENT CINNAMIC ACID DERIVATIVES

Compd.*	Substitution						Molecular descriptors			log (MIC)	
	P	Q	R	S	T	X	log P	${}^2\chi^v$	$1/{}^1IC$	<i>T. rubrum</i>	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>
1	H	H	H	H	H	H	2.130	2.082	2.497	(ni)	(ni)
2	OCH ₃	H	H	H	H	H	2.060	2.445	2.861	0.301	0.698
3	(trans) OCH ₃	H	H	H	H	CH ₃	2.880	2.891	2.507	0.256	0.544
4	(trans) OCH ₃	H	H	H	H	O ₂ H ₅	2.920	2.915	2.606	0.176	0.602
5	OH	H	H	H	H	H	1.460	2.263	2.846	1.778	(ni)
6	OCOCH ₃	H	H	H	H	H	2.110	2.884	2.942	1.903	1.929
7	OH	OH	H	H	H	H	0.860	2.242	2.970	1.230	1.398
8	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	H	H	H	2.328	2.786	2.873	2.19	No data
9	OCOCH ₃	OCOCH ₃	H	H	H	H	2.420	3.565	3.003	2.230	2.13
10	OCH ₃	OH	H	H	H	H	1.474	2.603	3.053	2.255	2.00
11	OCH ₃	OCOCH ₃	H	H	H	H	2.134	3.176	3.037	1.699	1.477
12	OH	OCH ₃	H	H	H	H	1.474	2.603	3.053	2.146	1.903
13	OCOCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	H	H	H	2.134	3.176	3.037	2.218	1.699
14	OH	Br	H	H	H	H	2.320	3.248	3.041	2.342	No data
15	OH	Br	H	Br	H	H	3.460	4.091	3.122	1.342	1.301
16	O—CH ₃ —O		H	H	H	H	1.328	2.784	3.0776	2.544	No data
17	H	H	OCH ₃	H	H	H	2.060	2.445	2.8608	0.903	0.745
18	o-Methoxycinnamaldehyde						1.843	2.278	2.495	1.079	1.176
19	(cis) OCH ₃	H	H	H	H	C ₂ H ₅	2.920	2.915	2.606	(ni)	(ni)
20	(cis) OCH ₃	H	H	H	H	OH ₂	2.880	2.891	2.507	(ni)	(ni)

*As in Sl. no. of Table 1. (ni) = No inhibition of growth of the test organisms.

development of resistant mutant against these compounds is high and consequently its communication may lead to clinical hazard. Thus the need for new antifungal compounds still persists.

We reported earlier the isolation, purification and synthesis of EPMC, a broad spectrum antimicrobial compound active against saprophytic filamentous fungi, dermatophytes, plant pathogens and pathogenic and non-pathogenic yeasts¹⁻³. In the present communication we have tried to rationalise the antifungal property of the 'lead' compound, EPMC, and its nineteen other structural analogues from a QSAR study with ultimate objective to design more useful antifungal compounds.

During last few years the works of Hansch *et al.*¹⁰, Randic¹⁶, Kier *et al.*^{11,17,18} and Ray *et al.*^{12,19} have shown that $\log P$, $^2\chi^v$ and 1IC of bioactive molecules are very useful lipophilic, electronic and steric parameters, respectively, and they can correlate the different biological responses of diverse group of chemical compounds. In our present study we have tried to elucidate the antifungal activity of the present series of compounds in terms of these molecular parameters. A review of Tables 3 and 4 and the regression equations involving $\log$ (MIC) and the said structural parameters suggest the following. (i) None of the steric, hydrophobic or electronic parameter alone can account for the biological (antifungal) response. A combination of two (or more) parameters is always necessary indicating the involvement of more

TABLE 4—BIPARAMETRIC CORRELATION MATRIX

	$^2\chi^v$	$1/^1IC$	$\log P$
$^2\chi^v$	1.00	0.4534	0.6189
$1/^1IC$	0.4534	1.00	0.029
$\log P$	0.6189	0.029	1.00

than one factor for the biological response. (ii) For *T. rubrum*, the regression equation involving $\log$ (MIC) with $^2\chi^v$ and ($1/^1IC$) provides the best statistically significant equation. Since $^2\chi^v$ is an electronic and 1IC , a topological steric parameter, it suggests that the stereo-electronic make-up and topology of the bioactive molecule is a major determinant for the bioresponse. The importance of steric fit or geometric complementarity is also indicated by the experimental fact that in this series only the *trans*-isomer is biologically active. The position of hydrogen atoms across the double bond is a key factor for the antifungal property of EPMC since by reduction of double bond or conversion into *cis*-isomer by uv exposure⁷ results in total loss of antifungal activity²⁰. Rinderknecht²¹ and Schraufstatter²² showed that side chain arrangement like $-C=C-CO-$ has proved to be very reactive in blocking sulphhydryl groups in protein (enzyme) and is necessary for biological activity of many antibiotic compounds. The presence of such a group in this series of compounds

suggests similar a 'group specific' steric fit. (iii) The presence of OCH_3 group in *para*-position with respect to the side chain results in a further increase in electron density in positions *ortho* and *para* with respect to the OCH_3 group and moreover, the key atom oxygen of OCH_3 group adjacent to the aromatic nucleus has one lone-pair of electron. The resonance effect gives rise to increased electron density in the *ortho*- and *para*-positions further. Formation of centres with high electron density in compounds sl. nos. 7, 14, 15 and 17 (Table 1) creates favourable electronic charge density environment and may be the reason for bioactivity of the compound. Since this effect is less pronounced in compounds sl. nos. 8 and 9 (Table 1), their MIC values are higher, as expected. Again the side chain and the aromatic moiety forms a conjugated system thereby facilitating the formation of a possible charge transfer complex of the biologically active molecule with the biotarget or the receptor²³. All these indicate the possible role of a steric as well as electronic parameters in the bioresponse of these compounds. Table 3 shows that the values of molecular parameters for *cis*- and *trans*-EPMC are identical, although they differ widely in their biological response. This reflects a weakness of the molecular descriptors used in the present study. The incapability of the molecular parameters for isomer discrimination demands the search for new descriptors. However, the fact that the regression equation with any singular molecular descriptor/parameter does not yield statistically significant equation while a combination of two or more is always necessary for it, strongly suggests that steric parameter alone is not capable to account for the desired bioresponse. A simultaneous role of a steric as well as an electronic parameters is necessary for the desired bioresponse. (iv) It is interesting to note that equations (1) and (4) do not yield statistically significant correlation of high degree. This implies that for both the test organisms, for bioresponse, $\log P$ hardly plays any significant role or the transport of the compound to the biotarget is not the only decisive factor for bioresponse in the present case. Similar observation was reported by Samanta *et al.*²⁴ for antifungal response of a series of phenolic compounds. For the present series of compounds, we observe for reasonable bioactivity (MIC) 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, the value of $\log P$ lies between 2.06 and 2.91. (v) A comparison of the equations (1-3) for *S. cerevisiae* with equations (4-6) for *T. rubrum* suggests that the mechanism of action of the test compounds against these two organisms are different. This difference in mode of action may be due to the difference in growth pattern, as *T. rubrum*, a mycelial fungus, multiplies by vegetative growth of mycelium and vegetative conidiospore formation primarily in presence of oxygen. *S. cerevisiae* under the experimental condition multiplies mainly by budding and can also grow under anaerobic condition. Moreover, their possible detoxification mechanism for this series of compounds may also be different. For *T. rubrum*, equation (5) ($r=0.858$)

and this statistically extremely significant biparametric multiple regression equation may be utilised in rationalising the process of substituent selection more fruitfully. Hence it may provide a good ground to rationalise the designing of more potent antifungal compounds of cinnamic acid derivative series.

References

1. S. GUPTA and A. B. BANERJEE, *Indian J. Exptl. Biol.*, 1970, **8**, 148.
2. S. K. GUPTA and A. B. BANERJEE, *Econ. Bot (USA)*, 1972, **26**, 255.
3. S. K. GUPTA, A. B. BANERJEE and B. ACHARI, *Lloydia*, 1976, **39**, 218.
4. P. N. KURIEN, K. C. PANDYA and V. R. SURANGE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 828.
5. K. C. PANDYA and T. A. VAHIDY, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1936, **4**, 134.
6. H. SONN and B. MÜLLER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1919, **52**, 1927.
7. I. L. FINAR, "Organic Chemistry", 5th ed., E.L.B.S., London, 1960, Vol. I, p. 736.
8. J. B. COHEN, "Practical Organic Chemistry", MacMillan, London, 1949, p. 249.
9. G. C. NYS and R. F. REKKER, *Chem. Therap.*, 1973 **8**, 521.
10. C. H. HANSCH and A. J. LEO, "Substituent Constant for Correlation Analysis in Chemistry and Biology", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1979.
11. L. B. KIER and L. H. HALL, "Molecular Connectivity in Chemistry Drug Research", Academic, New York, 1976.
12. R. SARKAR, A. B. ROY and P. K. SARKAR, *Math. Biosci.*, 1978, **39**, 299.
13. S. K. RAY, S. C. BASAK, C. RAYCHAUDHURY, A. B. ROY and J. J. GHOSH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, **20**, 894.
14. C. E. SHANON and W. WEAVER, 'Mathematical Theory of Communication', University of Illinois Press, Urbana, 1949.
15. A. K. DHAR and S. K. BOSE, *Appl. Microbiol.*, 1968, **16**, 340.
16. M. RANDIC, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **97**, 6609.
17. L. B. KIER and L. H. HALL, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1976, **65**, 1805.
18. W. J. MURRY, L. H. HALL and L. B. KIER, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1975, **64**, 1978.
19. S. K. RAY, S. C. BASAK, C. RAYCHAUDHURY, A. B. ROY and J. J. GHOSH, *Arzneim.-Forsch.*, 1983, **33**, 352.
20. S. K. GUPTA, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Calcutta, 1972.
21. H. BINDERKNECHT, J. L. WARD, F. BERGEL and A. L. MORRISON, *Biochem. J.*, 1947, **41**, 463.
22. E. SCHRAUFSTÄTTER, R. RICHTER and W. DITCHELD, *Arch. Dermatol. Syph.*, 1949, **188**, 259, E. SCHRAUFSTÄTTER and H. H. BRENT, *Nature (London)*, 1949, **164**, 456.
23. E. J. ARIENS, "Drug Design" (Medicinal Chemistry), Academic, New York, 1971, Vol. I, p. 196.
24. A. K. SAMANTA, S. K. RAY, S. C. BASAK and S. K. BOSE, *Arzneim.-Forsch.*, 1982, **32**, 12.
25. J. C. KRANTZ and C. J. OARR, "Pharmacologic Principles of Medicinal Practice", William Wilkins Co., Baltimore, 1969, p. 906.